

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON EASTERN WOMEN

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Abstract

As we know, globalization is a process of increasing interconnection and dependence of world economies, cultures, political systems and social structures. Globalization is defined as the process of rapid development and integration of social, cultural, economic and political relations throughout the world. This process, as in the whole world, has led to changes in various spheres of life in the societies of Eastern countries. The impact of globalization on Eastern women has occurred in several ways. During the globalization period, the role of Eastern women in society has also changed. Women are more socially and culturally active in society. Women are more organized to demand their rights and defend their social rights. Women's influence in the media has increased, and their role in the cultural sphere has become more recognized.

Keywords: globalization, oriental woman, education, economy, social inequality, values

The problem of women, as an inseparable subject of philosophy, is one of the most important topics that always make humanity think. Regardless of which direction human thought is directed, whether in the East or the West, the ultimate goal is still human life and existence itself. In the East, the existence of women has been studied, and in the West, its essence. For this reason, even today, in the East and the West, different opinions are expressed about women in terms of content. The Eastern worldview considers women to be a noble being, sanctifies them and tries to protect them by exalting them. The Western world, on the other hand, sees the protection of women in their development within society. Although in the East, women are considered to have all the human qualities created by God, they have been as far from taking an active role in society as possible. In the Western worldview, the issue of equality between women and men has expanded, especially since the Renaissance, and it seems that all thoughts have been directed towards sexual difference. Women are a symbol of modesty in the East. That is why the main work of a woman is the family and all the steps taken for its formation. In the East, the freedom of a woman is considered to consist of her work, which is praised in the family. In the East, a woman is a real hard worker. In the East, although a woman's work and presence in public life are not completely forbidden, they have always been considered secondary issues. In the East, a woman has a hidden character, and by protecting her, she is treated as if she is protecting the entire family and the future. In the East, a woman is presented as an example of simplicity, care, delicacy and a kind of elegance. In the West, a woman is formed as if in a struggle with the opposite sex and is characterized as if there is a competition between them.

To understand the impact of the globalization process on Eastern countries, it is first necessary to understand what globalization is and how it has developed in Eastern society. Globalization refers to the process of

rapid growth and mutual integration of economic, political, social and cultural relations on a global scale. This phenomenon has significantly changed the position and life of women in Eastern societies. Due to globalization, women have had wider educational and work opportunities, and have become more represented in social and cultural spheres.

Before globalization, the role of women in Eastern societies was often limited. Traditionally, women were responsible for family affairs, and their participation in wider areas of society decreased. However, with globalization, certain changes began to occur in this structure.

Eastern countries have historically been closed societies and in many cases were governed by traditional values. However, since the end of the 20th century, globalization has begun to rapidly change these societies. Globalization has led to major changes in terms of women entering the workforce, receiving education, and gaining economic independence. These changes have both positive and negative effects. The impact of such changes is evident both at the individual level and at the broader societal level.

An important impact of globalization is the progress of women in the field of education. In connection with globalization, women's education has been provided with easier access to both local and international educational opportunities. Serious changes have taken place in the field of women's education in many Eastern countries. Women are now receiving higher education and have begun to play a more active role in scientific fields, management and politics. It is very important for girls to get an education. An educated woman means an educated nation, an educated generation. In Azerbaijan, the issues of women's education, the elimination of illiteracy among women, women's health, and ensuring their economic freedom have always remained relevant.

One of the most effective aspects of globalization on Eastern women is the economic impact. Globalization opens up new opportunities for women in the labor market, stimulates their participation in the economy and creates new jobs.

In Eastern countries, the entry of women into the labor force has been possible with globalization. New trade relations, international investments and technological developments have ensured the entry of women into the labor market. Women have also begun to participate more in entrepreneurial activities. Opportunities have also been created for women to work independently in the global market.

Globalization leads to the expansion of labor migration, easier access to the international labor market, and, as a result, increased participation of women in various economic sectors. Eastern women, for example, become active participants in not only national but also international economic processes, as they operate in such areas as the garment industry, information technology, education, and healthcare. While in Eastern countries, entrepreneurial activity for women has traditionally been limited, globalization creates opportunities for them to create their own businesses. This extends from small and medium-sized enterprises to startups in the field of technology and services. Modern technologies and the Internet allow women to work anywhere in the world, which significantly increases their economic independence.

Despite all these developments, women in some Eastern countries still face some problems in the labor market. These include lower salaries compared to men, difficulties in career development, and the predominance of "female" professions, which are usually low-paid.

Globalization leads to improved educational opportunities for Eastern women. Knowledge exchange, the development of international educational programs, and online courses offer women new opportunities to improve their knowledge and obtain higher education. Many Eastern women are now able to study abroad or online, which was not possible in previous times.

Supporting programs for women's participation in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) fields have become an important aspect of globalization. In Eastern countries, especially India and Turkey, women are becoming more actively involved in technical and scientific research.

The Internet and digital technologies create great opportunities for Eastern women to educate themselves and facilitate education. Online courses, educational platforms and webinars make education more accessible. Globalization also affects the social and cultural life of Eastern women. Globalization leads to the mixing of cultures and social changes, which change how women perceive their role in society. The influence of Western culture is changing traditional norms and perceptions of women's place in society. Women are increasingly beginning to assert their rights, participate in public life and fight for gender equality. Women's influence in the media has increased and their role in the cultural sphere has become more recognized. Modern Western ideas,

such as gender equality in the family, mutual participation in housework and raising children, are beginning to penetrate Eastern societies. In some countries, women now play the primary role in raising children and doing housework, which is leading to changes in family structure.

The impact of globalization on Eastern women has been positive, with women making progress in economic independence, education, and social life.

The negative side of globalization has been the pressure on traditional family structures and women's roles in society in some Eastern societies. Although the influence of Western culture on the East has encouraged women to be more independent and individualistic, this has sometimes led to conflict with traditional family values. While the role of Eastern women in the family was more prominent in the past, globalization has increased women's activity in other areas of society.

Along with globalization, the presentation of women in advertising and commercial worlds with sexist stereotypes has increased. Many advertisements and media content portray women as attractive and sexually attractive images. This can negatively affect the psychological state of Eastern women and reinforce stereotypes that reflect their place in real life.

Changing traditional female roles, stereotyping, and economic inequality are some of the challenges faced by Eastern women. In order for Eastern women to become even more powerful in the future, social policies and reforms should be implemented to both benefit from the positive aspects and protect against negative effects.

The effects of globalization are still ongoing, and there are potential opportunities for Eastern women to become more independent and powerful in the future. The rights of Eastern women should be further expanded in the future. Women's suffrage, equality in the workplace, and stricter laws against domestic violence should be adopted.

Eastern societies can strengthen the social position of women by both preserving traditional values and taking advantage of the positive effects of globalization. This is possible by protecting both the economic independence of modern women and traditional family and social structures.

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